

Scorbutus

In: Lectures on the Theory and Practice of Medicine

Lancet 1838;(Sep 15):849-857.¹

by **Marshall Hall**

A short old summary of scurvy.

Yellow is used to indicate the more important sections such as the symptoms of scurvy.

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2026-2-12

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Hemilä.

¹ [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(02\)96153-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(02)96153-2)

Marshall Hall's comments on scurvy were cited by **K Codell Carter** in the following context:²

In the early nineteenth century, scurvy and rickets were generally believed to be diet-related. In 1830 the *Lancet* contained a series of 'Clinical lectures' by John Elliotson,³ Professor of Medicine in University College, London. In discussing scurvy, Elliotson noted that "the cause ... is always, I believe, a want of fresh animal and fresh vegetable food." About seven years later, in a similar lecture, Marshall Hall observed "scorbutus is generally induced by a deficiency of fresh vegetable food. It is also occasionally referred to other errors in diet, to the respiration of a crowded or otherwise impure atmosphere, to excessive fatigue, anxiety, etc.... The prevention and cure of scorbutus consists in the administration of fresh [animal?] and vegetable food, and, above all, of citric acid." Both men refer to Gilbert Blane and to James Lind whose works were, by that time, the recognized sources on scurvy. Neither Elliotson nor Hall suggests that his views are new or atypical; indeed, both men acknowledged that lemon juice had been the standard cure for scurvy for more than 200 years.

In 1840 George Budd⁴ summarized clinical knowledge of scurvy in an article in Alexander Tweedie's *A system of practical medicine*. Budd discussed various fruits and vegetables that were generally known to cure scurvy...

This is quite a misleading description of the history of scurvy.

Elliotson (1830) and Budd (1840) proposed that scurvy was caused by something missing in food, something that was in fruit and vegetables. That was not a fully novel idea, since Bachstrom (1734)⁵ had already proposed that:

This evil [scurvy] is solely owing to a total abstinence from fresh vegetable food, and greens; which is alone the true primary cause of the disease. And where persons, either through neglect or from necessity, refrain for a considerable time from eating the fresh fruits of the earth, and greens, no age, no climate or soil, are exempted from its attack.

2 Carter KC. The germ theory, beriberi, and the deficiency theory of disease. *Med Hist.* 1977;21(2):119-36. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/325303>

3 Elliotson J. Clinical lecture [on scurvy]. *Lancet* 1831;(Feb 12):649-655. <https://zenodo.org/records/15863946>
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(02\)95303-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(02)95303-1)

4 Budd G. Scurvy. 1840. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17455962>

5 Description of scurvy by Bachstrom (1734). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17225782>

James Lind firmly *disagreed* with Bachstrom's supposition. Lind wrote (1772):^{5, 6}

Others, again have supposed such to be the constitution of the human body, that health and life cannot be preserved long, without the use of green herbage, vegetables and fruits; and that a long abstinence from these, is alone the cause of the disease (Bachstrom).

But if this were truly the case, we must have had the scurvy very accurately described by the antients; whose chief study seems to have been the art of war; and whose manner of besieging towns was generally by blockade, till they had forced a surrender by famine. Now, as they held out many months, sometimes years, without a supply of vegetables: we should, no doubt, have heard of many dying of the scurvy, long before the magazines of dry provisions were exhausted. The continuance of those sieges far exceeded most of our modern ones; even the five months blockade of *Thorn*, upon which *Bachstrom* had founded this supposition. It would likewise be a much more frequent disease in every country, than it really is: for there are persons every where, who, from choice, eat few or no green vegetables; and some countries are deprived of the use of them for five or six months of the year; as is the case of many parts in the highlands of *Scotland*, *Newfoundland*, &c. where, however, the scurvy is unusual.

In the text by Marshall Hall (1838)(see the last page of this document), to which Carter referred to, Hall does not make an argument that it is *solely* the lack of “fresh vegetable food” that is crucial for causing scurvy in the way Bachstrom (1734) proposed. Instead, Hall wrote: “It is also occasionally referred to other errors in diet, to the respiration of a crowded or otherwise impure atmosphere, to excessive fatigue, anxiety, &c.” and he does not state that these explanations are erroneous.

Kenneth Carpenter (1986) commented Lind's treatise:⁷

The treatise begins with a “critical history” of the subject, and has, as Part III (a kind of appendix to the book), a synopsis of each of the earlier publications on scurvy that Lind had been able to discover. This is impressive and scholarly work, and, wherever I have been able to compare his summary with the original, it appears objective and accurate. p.54.

After reading Lind's brilliant review of other people's ideas, which was so much ahead of its time, one turns eagerly to his own theory of the disease. But this is extremely difficult – even painful – to read, let alone summarize, and few have attempted it. p.57.

Jeremy Baron (2009) summarized Lind's views about the etiology of scurvy as follows:⁸

Lind clearly stated Kramer and Bachstrom's unitary fresh vegetables hypothesis for cause and cure of scurvy. However, his own chapters on the causes and cures of scurvy

6 <https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/50/mode/2up>

7 Carpenter KJ (1986) *The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C*.

<https://www.cambridge.org/fi/universitypress/subjects/history/history-medicine/history-scurvy-and-vitamin-c>

8 Baron JH. Sailors' scurvy before and after James Lind – a reassessment. *Nutr Rev.* 2009;67(6):315-32. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19519673>

are full of obscure and uncritical concepts, and one is left with his ideas that sea scurvy was due to excess perspiration, could be prevented by ventilation, and that many remedies could be used as well as citrus fruits and cresses.

Carter also wrote:

Neither Elliotson nor Hall suggests that his views are new or atypical.

This is not a sound argument. Lack of stating that one's opinion is not generally accepted does not indicate that the person's opinion actually is generally accepted. There were controversies about the cause of scurvy up to the early twentieth century.

For example, Elmer McCollum – one of the most influential nutrition researchers in the twentieth century⁹ – was convinced that scurvy was caused by constipation.^{10, 11} Sir Almroth Wright – famous immunologist¹² – was convinced that scurvy was caused by blood being insufficiently alkaline.^{13, 14} It was only in 1937, when Holt showed him that if scorbutic guinea-pigs were given pure crystalline ascorbic acid they were cured of experimental scurvy and this substance could prevent the condition, that Wright capitulated.^{15, 16} Given that the fruit and vegetable explanation was not generally accepted in the early twentieth century, it is evident that there was no general consensus during the nineteenth century, see detailed history by Carpenter.⁷

In any case, Marshall Hall's text is historically interesting. Below is his section on scurvy.

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- 9 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Elmer_McCollum
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbm.1969.0008>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4879632>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4904501>
<https://www.nationalacademies.org/read/568/chapter/10#270>
 - 10 McCollum EV (1917) The "vitamine" hypothesis and deficiency diseases: a study of exerimental scurvy.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9258\(18\)86722-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9258(18)86722-9)
 - 11 McCollum EV (1918), The "vitamin" hypothesis and diseases referable to faulty diet. p. 937-940.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1918.02600380001001>
 - 12 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Almroth_Wright
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbm.1948.0032>
<https://history.rcp.ac.uk/inspiring-physicians/sir-almroth-edward-wright>
<https://doi.org/10.1038/159731a0>
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/768924>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20787115>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/13082064>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4612919>
 - 13 Wright AE (1900) On the pathology and therapeutics of scurvy.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(01\)99819-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(01)99819-8)
 - 14 Coplans M. (1904). On the etiology of scurvy.
See Almroth Wright's comments on p.94-97, 108-109.
eg. "nothing in pathology is to my mind more certainly established, than that the essential essence of scurvy is to be found in a diminution of the alkalinity of the blood." p.95.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18621256>
 - 15 Lewis HE (1972)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc1644345>
 - 16 Holt LB (1972)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc1644320>

V.— SCORBUTUS.

I. *The History.*—Scorbutus is generally induced by a deficiency of fresh vegetable food. It is also occasionally referred to other errors in diet, to the respiration of a crowded or otherwise impure atmosphere, to excessive fatigue, anxiety, &c.

II. Scorbutus is usually distinguished by a set of symptoms designated by the term *putrescent*, such as a spongy and ulcerated state of the gums, with extreme fœtor of the breath; gangrenous ulcers; a fœtid state of the urine, &c.

The countenance and skin generally become peculiarly pale and sallow, or yellowish and tumid; there are extreme debility; a disposition to somnolency, to syncope, &c.; shortness of breathing; a feeble pulse, &c. Petechiæ and vibices appear on various parts of the body; the gums bleed; former cicatrices are dissolved, and the ulcerated surfaces bleed, and perhaps slough; there is hæmorrhage from the bowels, the kidney or bladder, the uterus, &c.; serous effusions take place into the cellular membrane and the cavities.

III. *The Morbid Anatomy* of scorbutus consists of the effusion of blood, or of bloody serum, or of serum alone, into the various parenchymatous textures, or serous cavities of the body, or from the mucous membranes; of an uncoagulable condition of the blood, and of softening of the solids.

IV. *The Prevention* and the cure of scorbutus consists in the administration of fresh and vegetable food, but, above all, of citric acid.

Sir Gilbert Blane observes—“The scurvy, a disorder incident chiefly to a sea life, but by no means peculiar to it, has been nearly eradicated by lemon juice, or more properly the citric acid; for the juice of limes, Seville oranges, unripe China oranges, and in short of all the species of the botanical genus citrus, or the natural order of fruit called *Hesperidæi*, possess the same virtue. This was known to be a remedy for the scurvy, far superior to all others, two hundred years ago, as appears by the writings of Woodall. It is singular that this im-

portant fact should have been hardly known for more than one hundred years afterwards, when the late Dr. Lind, of Haslar hospital, revived and diffused this valuable piece of knowledge by his writings. It was this author who first clearly stated the singular powers of this remedy in the cure of scurvy; for Woodall only affirmed that its virtues were far superior to all other remedies. Notwithstanding this, the Navy continued to suffer severely from this disease, till the order for a general supply of lemon juice, twenty-seven years ago. This salutary measure was accomplished by a representation from the Medical Board of the Navy in the year 1795, during the administration of Earl Spencer, from whose enlarged and benevolent mind everything was to be expected. One of the most impressive parts of their argument, was built on the report of the effects of it in the Suffolk of 74 guns. This ship sailed from England on the second of April 1764, and an experiment was made of supplying her with a quantity of lemon juice sufficient to serve out two-thirds of a liquid ounce every day, to every man on board. This was mixed with their grog, along with two ounces of sugar. She was twenty-three weeks and one day on the passage, without having any communication with the land, and arrived in Madras roads on the 11th of September, without losing a man, with only fifteen men on the sick list, all slight cases, and none of them affected with the scurvy. This disease appeared in a few men in the course of the voyage, but soon disappeared on an increased dose of lemon juice being administered. Let this fact be contrasted with the state of the Channel fleet in 1780, as described by Dr. Lind, which was over-run with scurvy and fever, and unable to keep the sea, after a cruise of ten weeks only: and let the state of this fleet be again contrasted with that of the Channel fleet in 1800, as described by Dr. Baird, which, by being duly supplied with lemon juice, kept the sea for four months without fresh provisions, and without being affected with scurvy.